

ANTHROPOMETRIC STUDIES STOP MILITARY PERSONNEL OF THE MILITARY ACADEMY

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Annotation: *In this article, anthropometric studies have been carried out and the relationship between the dimensional features of the foot of military personnel has been determined. Developed dimensional-full assortment. As a result of the measurements, the dynamics of growth in the length of the foot was determined depending on the age.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье проведены антропометрические исследования и определена связь между размерными признаками стопы военнослужащих. Разработан размерный-полнотный ассортимент. В результате измерений определена динамика роста длины стопы в зависимости от возраста.*

We have carried out anthropometric studies of the feet and lower legs of servicemen. In the course of the measurements, 400 employees at the military academy were examined, of which 210 cadets from 17 to 26 years old are cadets. In work

The states of the longitudinal and transverse arches, as well as the shape of the anterior section of the feet of military personnel were determined;

-average parameters of the feet were determined and regression dependencies between the main parameters of the lower extremities were established;

In order to improve the quality of footwear for military personnel, the following issues are considered: carrying out anthropometric studies of the feet of military personnel in order to correct outdated dimensional typology.

The values of the following dimensional features were determined: foot girth along the outer and inner beams (Opn, Opv). Based on the plantography method, the longitude and latitude parameters of the feet were established.[1]

Statistical indicators of the distribution of the feet sizes of military personnel are shown in the table.

Table 1

Anthropometric indicators	Foot length , mm M±m	Outer beam width , mm M±m	Inner beam width , mm M±m	heel width, mm M±m	Cut off in bundles beam , mm M±m
Return	of the military				
17	250±0,1	97±0,6	97±0,6	66±0,1	195,2
18	253±0,9	97±0,2	95±0,8	61±0,7	194,4
19	253±0,7	97±0,2	95±0,9	62±0,6	194,4
20	252±0,3	97±0,4	95±0,4	69±0,2	194,8
21	246±0,4	99±0,7	96±0,2	66±0,8	199,4
22	253±0,8	95±0,5	94±0,4	62±0,4	190

23	255±0,1	109±0,9	107±0,1	70±0,1	218
24	257±0,5	107±0,5	105±0,1	73±0,1	215
25	262±0,1	102±0,8	104±0,7	69±0,8	205
26	272±0,5	103±0,5	105±0,1	67±0,5	207

As a result of the processing of anthropometric data, the equations for the relationship between age and dimensional features of the feet were calculated.

Fig1. Diagrams of the dynamics of foot development by age, a-length of the foot, b-width of the outer beam, c-width of the inner beam, d-width of the heel.

The diagram shows the growth dynamics of foot length depending on age. The data indicate that the length of the foot of the measured military personnel increases from 225 to 285 mm. During this period, the length of the foot increases by 60 mm. The greatest increase in the length of the foot is observed at the age of 20-21 years and is 285 mm.

The foot, as the most loaded part of the musculoskeletal system, develops and changes its shape throughout a person's life. [2-3]

The width of the outer beam from 17 to 26 years increases from 98 mm to

104 mm (picture 2). During this period of time, the width of the outer beam increases by 35 mm.

Thus, with age, the average relative increase in foot width is less than the corresponding increase in foot length. The average width of the outer beam is relatively uniform and is 2-4 mm.

Analysis of the data shows that the values of all studied signs of the foot gradually change with age. The measurement of the width of the inner beam is shown in Figure 3. From the data shown, it can be seen that the width of the inner beam at 17 years old is on average 96 mm and

26 years increases to 104 mm. The greatest growth observed in the width of the inner beam in the period from 24 to 26 years is 2.7 mm. The results of measuring the width of the heel are shown in Figure 4. From the above data, it can be seen that the width of the heel at 17 years old is 63 mm. Then it gradually increases and reaches 26 years to 68 mm. The data obtained allow us to judge the ratio of the size of the feet by age.

To establish the relationship between the main dimensional features of the foot and the age of the subjects, the regression equation is calculated at the next stage. [4-5].

Taking into account changes in the dimensions along the length and width of the feet of military personnel, changes are being made in the design of lasts to create rational footwear.

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